

Rapid measurement of pasture evapotranspiration components using proximal sensors

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Background

Evapotranspiration (ET) is the total amount of water released by a crop or pasture canopy in the form of Transpiration (T) and Evaporation (E). ET accounts for up to 96% of the water loss depending on the types of vegetation cover and climatic conditions (Wilcox *et al.*, 2003). Transpiration is related to the productivity of crops and pasture; whereas, evaporation is the loss of water directly from soil surface. Estimating separately the components of ET in the field is challenging yet it is highly significant in terms of improving crop water use and irrigation efficiency, since a anywhere between 30 and 80% of the water flux can be associated with the all-important evaporation component (Wilcox *et al.*, 2003). Sap flow monitoring, using micro-lysimeters or isotopic analysis are the usual options for separately measuring transpiration and evaporation in plants but these are incompatible with in-situ field deployment. In this study a portable and convenient method for separately determining the evapotranspiration components has been developed. When coupled with widely-used active optical sensors, the device can be used to develop, in-situ, relationships between spectro-optical indices such as NDVI and evapotranspiration coefficients (K_c , K_{cb} and K_e) that characterize actual ET water loss relative to evaporative demand.

Methods

A 0.5 m diameter, portable, perspex dome was equipped with temperature and humidity sensors and a circulating fan to calculate the rate of vapour accumulation inside the chamber when placed over a target pasture canopy (*Festuca arundinacea* var. Dovey). When deployed it takes less than a minute to measure the actual evapotranspiration rate (Alam *et al.*, 2018). Repeating the measurement over an adjacent area of similar pasture cover but with zero photosynthesis, for example in response to the application of a fast-acting herbicide, provided an estimate of the evaporation component when the soil moisture condition was maintained similar to that of the active plant canopy. Using reference crop evapotranspiration (ET_o) data collected from a nearby weather station yielded the evapotranspiration coefficient (K_c) and soil evaporation coefficient (K_e). The basal crop coefficient (K_{cb}) was then calculated following the FAO dual crop coefficient equation, i.e ($K_c=K_{cb}+K_e$) (Allen *et al.*, 1998). Optical vegetation properties (NDVI and LAI) were also recorded from the same target pasture canopy with the help of handheld optical sensors (Green Seeker and LAI Ceptometer) to explore the relationship of evapotranspiration coefficients with NDVI and LAI.

Results and conclusion

The values of crop coefficients and the relevant optical parameters (NDVI and LAI) are plotted in Figure 1 (a) and (b), respectively to demonstrate the relationship between the crop coefficients and optical parameters under non-water limiting conditions.

Figure 2. Relationship between crop coefficients and optical vegetation parameters (a) NDVI and (b) LAI at non-limiting soil moisture condition.

The crop coefficient (K_c) was found to be nonlinear against both NDVI and LAI with a strong correlation ($R^2=0.93$ and 0.88 for NDVI and LAI respectively) although the pattern is quite different. The K_e was found to be very little influenced with the increase of vegetation cover may be because the reason that moisture availability increase with the increase of vegetation while the energy reached to the soil decreased and balanced each other. However, the basal crop coefficient (K_{cb}) was revealed to be highly affected by the vegetation which contributed to the ratio (K_{cb}/K_c) to be varied from 0.03 to 0.46 for zero to the highest available vegetation cover. This range of value indicated that the soil evaporation could contribute as high as 56% even when the LAI is more than 4, because the water availability on top soil did not limit the soil evaporation at high LAI. Such higher loss of water due to evaporation is also evident in other research findings, especially for pasture and rangeland areas (Kool *et al.*, 2014). The method includes simple instrumentation and least amount of data to successfully isolate the evapotranspiration components and visualized how they interact with the optical characteristics of pasture canopy.

References

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